

AN EXAMINATION OF AL-KINDI'S CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE FIELD OF PHILOSOPHY.

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Abstract

Abu Yusuf Ya'qub Ibn Is-haq al-Kindi (801-873CE) was an Arab Iraqi polymath: an Islamic philosopher, scientist, astrologer, astronomer, cosmologist, chemist, logician, mathematician, musician, physician, psychologist, and meteorologist. Al-Kindi was the first Muslim Peripatetic philosopher, and is known for his efforts to introduce Greek and Hellenistic philosophy to the Arab world. He was a pioneer in chemistry, medicine, music theory, physics, psychology, the philosophy of science and also known for being one of the fathers of cryptography. This paper looks at the basis of Islamic Philosophy that is Qur'an and Hadith, the life history of al-Kindi, his philosophical thought, his teachings, some of his works, his contributions to the field of Islamic philosophy. He used his resources and knowledge of Greek and Syriac languages to translate, and he revised other works already translated by some philosophers. He taught some people and wrote many books on different aspect of philosophical sciences. He attempted to provide a philosophical basis for the speculative theory of the Mutazilites. His influence on Muslim thinkers continued for about a century after his death.

Introduction

Philosophy is a subject which deals with some of the most general questions about the universe and our place in it. It is quite different from science, because its questions cannot be answered empirically by observation or experiment, but its purpose is entirely intellectual. The first Islamic philosopher to emerge among the

Arabs was al-Kindi died and known as “the philosopher of the Arabs.”

Al-Kindi was born of noble Arabic descent and flourished in Iraq under the caliphs' al-Ma'mun (813-833 C.E) and al-Mu'tasim (833-842 C.E). He concerned himself not only with those philosophical questions that had been treated by the Aristotelian Neoplatonists of Alexandria but also with such miscellaneous subjects as astrology, medicine, Indian arithmetic, logogriphs, the manufacture of swords, and cooking. He is known to have written more than 270 works (mostly short treatises), a considerable number of which are extant, and some in Latin translations.

And Al-Kindi brought Science and Philosophy together by strongly emphasizing after the Pythagoreans and Plato that nobody could be a philosopher without being thoroughly disciplined in mathematics.

Definition of Philosophy

The term philosophy was coined from two Greek words '*philos*' and '*sophia*' which literally means “love of wisdom” when joined together (Sulaiman: 2001). When we talk of philosophy in the technical sense, it is an activity that engaged the minds of the philosophers like Plato, Kant and al-Ghazali, and still engages the minds of present philosophers. Harry Schofield defined philosophy as a process of asking questions (Sulaiman: 2001). Philosophy deals with questions that are not answered in science laboratories but through thinking. And Islamic philosophy is therefore, born out of rational thinking and investigation of certain questions and stipulations about man and Islam (Cyril: 2005).

Moreover, the first revelation to Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W) was a clear testimony and impetus to man to seek for true knowledge no matter where it may be available or found. Muslim philosophers were very busy with all things in general as long as human faculties can perceive such things. They relied mostly on their intellects to explain anything perceived. In fact, *al-Qur'an* itself can be viewed as a philosophical Book as well as scientific in nature. In short, it is an embodiment of all branches of knowledge. It was the Muslims themselves who drew the attention of non-Muslims to the philosophical aspect of the Qur'an (Ameer: 1978).

The first Muslim Philosopher to emerge was al-Kindi. His contribution to the development of philosophical studies was unique. He was the first to write an epistle to Caliph Mu'tasim (reign between 833 and 842CE) explaining to him what philosophical studies was all about and to justify its studies so that the official patronage of the *Baitu al-Hikmah* (House of wisdom) which was established by al-Ma'mun Ibn Haruna Rasheed, would continue and the Philosophers or those who have interest in those sciences could study them without any fear of official harassment due to the pressure of the jurists, scholars of Hadith and those that al-Kindi called men of religion (Nigerian Teacher Institute: 2000). That house of wisdom comprises of library, research centre, translation bureau, etc. al-Ma'mun established it with the aim of reserving the Muslim culture and learning as well as increase the Muslim literacy by employing some scholars who understood both Arabic and Greek languages to translate some Greek's works, especially, the philosophy into Arabic and these works were kept in the academy. (Solagberu: 2010).

Bases of Philosophy from Islamic Perspective

The bases of Islamic Philosophy from Islamic perspective are the Qur'an and *Sunnah*. This is because the two sources call on the Muslims neither to accept faith dogmatically, nor to behave blindly, ignorantly or without knowledge. Rather the two sources call on the Muslims to pursue and seek knowledge and at the same time to reason over matters. The Qur'an encourages the Muslims to develop the habits of enquiry, to become inquisitive, curious and investigative. It is for this reason the Qur'an specifically called on the Muslims to reflect, ponder, contemplate, analyze and reason, (Oloruntele: 2001) as contained in the following verses of the Glorious Qur'an:

Almighty Allah testified to this where He says:

﴿ قُلْ لَا أَقُولُ لَكُمْ عِنْدِي خَزَائِنُ اللَّهِ وَلَا أَعْلَمُ الْغَيْبِ وَلَا أَقُولُ لَكُمْ إِنِّي مَلَكٌ إِن اتَّبَعُوا إِلَّا مَا يُوْحَىٰ إِلَيْكَ قُلْ هَلْ يَسْتَوِي الْأَعْمَىٰ وَالْبَصِيرُ أَفَلَا تَتَفَكَّرُونَ ﴿٥٠﴾ الأنعام: ٥٠

Say: "I tell you not that with me are the Treasures of God, nor do I know what is hidden, nor do I tell you I an Angel. I but follow what is revealed to me." Say: "Can the blind be held equal to the seeing?" will ye then consider not? (surat al-An'am, 6:50)

﴿ أَوَلَمْ يَتَفَكَّرُوا فِي أَنفُسِهِمْ مَا خَلَقَ اللَّهُ السَّمَوَاتِ وَالْأَرْضَ وَمَا بَيْنَهُمَا إِلَّا بِالْحَقِّ وَأَجَلٍ مُّسَمًّى وَإِنَّ كَثِيرًا مِّنَ النَّاسِ بِلِقَائِ رَبِّهِمْ لَكٰفِرُونَ ﴾ الروم: ٨

Do they not reflect in their own minds? Not but for just ends and for a time appointed, did God create the heavens and earth, and all between them: yet are there truly many among men who deny the meeting with their Lord (at the Resurrection)! (Surat Rum, 30:8)

﴿ قُلْ هَلْ يَسْتَوِي الَّذِينَ يَعْلَمُونَ وَالَّذِينَ لَا يَعْلَمُونَ إِنَّمَا يَتَذَكَّرُ أُولُو الْأَلْبَابِ ﴾ الزمر: ٩

Say: "Are those equal, those who know and those who do not know? It is those who are endued with understanding that receive admonition. (Surat Zumar, 39: 9)"

The quoted verses extol the excellence of knowledge and demonstrate that the learned is not equal with the unlearned. The Qur'an went further to call on the Muslims to reflect and analyse the phenomenon of creation and to ponder over it and even if possible to examine how they were created. The above verses served as impetus for the Muslim to engage in the study of philosophy, and one of the great Muslim philosophers was al-Kindi (Lewis and others: 1965).

Pillars of Philosophy

There are three pillars of philosophy. They are: Logic, Epistemology and Metaphysics. According to Sulaiman: 2001, Logic is concerned with thought, rationality and the nature and working of a language as a tool for understanding the world. Epistemology or theory of knowledge is concerned with what constitute

knowledge, how it is acquired, verified and tested. Metaphysics deals with things that are beyond the physical world, it also deals with the essence and meaning of essence, search for ultimate reality and an inquiry about the destiny of man, among others.

Life History of al-Kindi

Al-Kindi was a native of Yemen and a descendant of the Kindah tribe which is a well known Arabic tribe. His full name was Abu Yusuf, Y'aqub Ibn Is-haq Ibn as-Sabbah Ibn 'Imran Ibn Isma'il Ibn al-Ash'ath Ibn Qaus al-Kindi (803-873 C.E). His grandfather al-Ash'ath was one of the Companions of the Prophet (S.A.W). He went to Kufa with some Companions and settled there with his descendants. He participated in the conquest of Persia and Iraq with Sa'ad Ibn Abi Waqqas. He led the Kindah tribe on the side of Ali (RA), the fourth Caliph (656-661C.E) at the famous battle of Siffin. Al-Kindi participated in public life and was made the governor of Kufah at the time of Abbasid caliph al-Mahdi and Harun ar-Rasheed (<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/AlKindi>).

Al-Kindi was born in 185AH/803C.E towards the end of his father's life time. It is interesting to remember that the twin town of Basrah and Kufah used to compete in educational excellence. Basrah was more disposed to textual proofs whereas Kufah was more inclined to rationalism. Al-Kindi received his preliminary education in Kufah and later completed his studies in Baghdad where he had more chance of studying the Sciences and Philosophy. He committed the whole al-Qur'an to memory. It was reported that in addition to Arabic, he also studied other language like Greek and Syriac to facilitate his quest for Hellenistic heritage (Badr: 1998).

Al-Kindi became a prominent figure in the House of Wisdom, and number of Abbasid Caliph appointed him to oversee the translation of Greek scientific and philosophical text into the Arabic Language. He served as a tutor to the son of Caliph al-Mu'tasim, al-Qifti, pointedly asserted that al-Kindi was skilled in the arts of the Greeks, the Persians and the Hindus. He gained insights in to the thought of Greek Philosophers, especially Aristotle, through the translation movement. His contact with the philosophy of the ancients had a profound effect on his intellectual

ethics and metaphysics to mathematics and pharmacology (Hitti: 1984).

Al-Kindi was famous in rational sciences and philosophy to which medical cases were referred to. He died in 873CE/260AH leaving behind vast literature in these fields for future generations to use.

His Philosophical Thoughts

Al-Kindi brought Science and Philosophy close together by strongly emphasizing after the Pythagoreans and Plato, that nobody could be a philosopher without being thoroughly disciplined in mathematics. He was very verse in mathematics, medicine, optics, music etc. According to him, Reason and prophecy are both equally important and valuable avenues for the knowledge of ultimate reality; it would be unfortunate to hold only one of them to be the sole avenue. He translated from Greek to Arabic and amended between Religion and Philosophy especially during his time when there was conflict between philosophers and jurist (Solagberu: 2010).

Al-Kindi as a philosopher had many works on the subject matter. His principal work on geometrical and physiological optics, based on the optics of Euclid in Theon's recession, was widely used in both the East and West until superseded by the greater work of Ibn Al-Haytham. Al-Kindi's three or four treatises on the theory of music are the earliest extant works in Arabic showing the influence of Greek writers on that subject. In one of these treatises, Al-Kindi describes rhythm as a constituent part of Arabic music. Measured song, or menstrual music must therefore have been known to the Muslim countries before it was introduced to Christian Europe (Sheikh: nd).

Al-Kindi connected the universe and all what it comprises with its great existentiality. He formed a theory which recognized how high existence influences lower existence. He submitted that it is possible to know the cause of everything by virtue of their inter-relationship. He regarded soul as immortal and imperishable. He maintained that soul directs the whole body and its non-existence results to the death of the body. Such a soul would later join the incorruptible world (Muhammad: 2000).

However, he submitted that the world of sense belongs to the physical world and the world of reasoning belongs to the spiritual world and a soul cannot be at rest until it turns to God spiritually (Sulaiman: 2001).

Assessment of al-Kindī's Philosophical Thought.

Although the first Muslim philosopher, al-Kindi, who flourished in the first half of the 9th century, lived during the triumph of the Muʿtazilah of Baghdad and was connected with the Abbâsid caliphs who championed the Muʿtazilah and patronized the Hellenistic sciences, there is no clear evidence that he belonged to a theological school. His writings show him to have been a diligent student of Greek and Hellenistic authors in philosophy and point to his familiarity with Indian arithmetic (Sharif: 1963).

His conscious and open acknowledgment of earlier contributions to scientific inquiry was foreign to the spirit, method, and purpose of the theologians of the time. His acquaintance with the writings of Plato and Aristotle was still incomplete and technically inadequate. He improved the Arabic translation of the "Theology of Aristotle" but made only a selective and circumspect use of it (Encyclopedia Britannica: 2010).

Devoting most of writings to questions of natural philosophy and mathematics, al-Kindī was particularly concerned with the relation between corporeal things, which are changeable, in constant flux, infinite, and as such unknowable, on the one hand, and the permanent world of forms (spiritual or secondary substances), which are not subject to flux yet to which man has no access except through things of the senses. He insisted that a purely human knowledge of all things is possible, through the use of various scientific devices, learning such things as mathematics and logic, and assimilating the contributions of earlier thinkers (Watt: 1987).

The existence of a "supernatural" way to this knowledge in which all these requirements can be dispensed with what acknowledged by al-Kindī: God may choose to impart it to His Prophets by cleansing and illuminating their souls and by giving them His aid, right guidance, and inspiration; and they, in turn, communicate it

to ordinary men in an admirably clear, concise, and comprehensible style. This is the prophets' "divine" knowledge, characterized by a special mode of access and style of exposition. In principle, however, this very same knowledge is accessible to man without divine aid, even though "human" knowledge may lack the completeness and consummate logic of the prophets' divine message (Encyclopedia Britannica: 2010).

Reflection on the two kinds of knowledge (the human knowledge bequeathed by the ancients and the revealed knowledge expressed in the Quran) led al-Kindi to pose a number of themes that became central to Islamic philosophy: the rational-metaphorical exegesis of the Quran and the hadith; the identification of God with the first being and the first cause; creation as the giving of being and as a kind of causation distinct from natural causation and Neoplatonic emanation; and the immortality of the individual soul (Sulaiman: 2003).

The Relationship between Revelation and Philosophy

In the view of al-Kindi prophecy and philosophy were two different routes to arrive at the truth. He contrasts the two positions in four ways. Firstly, while a person must undergo a long period of training and study to become a philosopher, prophecy is bestowed upon someone by God. Secondly, the philosopher must arrive at the truth by his own devices (and with great difficulty) whereas the prophet has the truth revealed to him by God. Thirdly, the understanding of the prophet -being divinely revealed- is clearer and more comprehensive than that of philosophy and fourthly, the way in which the prophet is able to express this understanding to the ordinary people is superior (Microsoft Encarta: 2009).

Therefore, al-Kindi submits that, the prophet is superior in the fields, the ease and certainty with which he receives the truth, and the way in which he presented it. However, the crucial implication is that the content of the Prophet's and Philosopher's knowledge is the same (Abu Hasan: 1979).

(i) Logic and Translation

Al-Kindi was an ethnic with an illustrious lineage going back to such near-mythic Arabian families as *Qays*. He was known as Philosopher of the Arabs in

contrast to the later Islamic philosophers who, though Muslim, were not Arabs and often learned Arabic as a second language. The early bibliographers gave his ancestry and a long list of works, many of which are no longer extant, but his personal life remains unknown. Although he is remembered for introducing philosophy to the Abbasid court, his skills covered many fields including medicine, mathematics, music, astrology and optics (<http://www.muslimphilosophy...>).

Al-Kindi used early Arabic Language translations of Greek philosophy, which enabled him to add part of the Hellenistic tradition to his programme. The founding of *Baytul-Hikmah* for the large-scale translation of documents from Greek, in the early 9th century meant both that the foreign sciences were available wholesale to Arabophone scholars and that there was serious interest in the knowledge they contained. Al-Kindi was occasionally credited (in the title inscription) with correcting the translation. A study of his terminology shows that al-Kindi was aware of particular terms used in Hellenistic philosophy, and of which Arabic word best expressed the same idea (Ma^oshood: nd).

(ii) Metaphysics

Al-Kindi's best known treatise is the metaphysical study, *Fi al-Falsafa al-Ula* (on first Philosophy). In this book, al-Kindi described the first philosophy, which is also the most noble and highest philosophy, as the knowledge of the first truth, including the cause of every truth (the first cause). The first cause is prior in time because it is the cause of time. By the study of philosophy, people will learn the knowledge of things in reality, and through this knowledge of the divinity of God and his Unity. They will also learn human virtue. Throughout many of his treatises, al-Kindi emphasizes the importance of the intellect (*'aql*) and contrast in matter (<http://www.muslim...>).

He also discusses the One Truth, which is another name for God, and states that it does not have any attribute, predicate or characteristics. Other aspects of his position include emphasis on the absolute unity of God, His power particularly as Creator and creation *ex nihilo*. The Eternal, that is God, is not due to another; He has no cause and has neither genus nor species. There is no 'before' for the Eternal. The Eternal is

unchanging, immutable and impressible. In human terms, death is the soul's taking leave of the body, which it employed during life. For al-Kindi, the intellect continues (Muhammad: 2000).

Al-Kindi differs from Hellenistic philosophical tradition primarily in espousing the belief that the world was created *ex nihilo*. In Aritotelian metaphysics the Prime Mover set the world in motion, but in Hellenistic tradition, time and motion are intrinsically linked. In al-Kindi's system, matter, time and movement are all finite, with a beginning and a cessation at some future point. In all the philosophical writings of al-Kindi, he does not so much direct arguments to the concerns of religion as avoid them altogether, instead describing the parallel universe of philosophy. He consistently tries to show that the pursuit of philosophy is compatible with orthodox of Islam (Sharif: 1963).

His works

Al-Kindi was a prolific writer; a number of works and total number are ascribed to him. However, only few of them are extant by now. The works are classified according to their subjects matter, although most of his works are short treatises. But on the whole, the works are put into seventeen classes as follows: Geometry, Mathematics, Music, Medicine, Meteorology, Logic, Astrology, Astronomy, Philosophy, Pharmacology, Physics, Psychology, Politics, and host of others. Notable among his works are:

- *Rasa'il al-Kindi al-falsafiya* (Philosophical Treatises of al-Kindi).
- *Al-Falsafat al-Ula* (On First Philosophy).
- *Risalah fi al-Hilah li-daf' al-Ahzan* (On the Art of Averting Sorrows).
- *Fi Hudud al-Ashya' wa-Rusumiha* (On the Definitions of Things and their Descriptions).
- *Fi Wahdaniya Allah wa Tunahiy jirm al-'Alam* (On the Unity of God and the Limitation of the Body of the World).
- *Fi Kammiya Kutub Aristutalis wa ma Yahtaju ilahi fi Tahsil al-Falsafa* (The Quantity of the Books of Aristotle and what is Required for the Acquisition of Philosophy) (<http://www.muslimphilosophy>).

Recommendations

Al-Kindi contributed immensely to the development of philosophy in the world, this made the researcher to recommend the followings:

- His works should be appreciated and the available ones should be translated into English for the consumption of the public because most of such works were translated into Arabic only.
- People should endeavour to imitate his life style which is very simple and worthy of emulation in terms of academic pursuit.
- His contributions to the field of Islamic Philosophy and others should be emulated.
- As Al-Kindi was a creative philosopher in his time which made his legacy to remain an exemplary for the seekers of knowledge at the present time.
- His works should be kept in the academy for onward consultation.

Conclusion

Conclusively, the first Muslim Philosopher was Al-Kindi of pure Arab descendant. His grandfather was a Companion of the Prophet who fought in the conquest of Persia and Iraq, and also the battles of Siffin and Nihrawan on side of Ali (R.A). His father was a governor of Kufah at one time. Al-Kindi had his early education in Kufah and later went to Baghdad where his fame spread. He contributed to the spread of the philosophical sciences by using his resources and knowledge of Greek and Syriac languages to translate and revised other works already translated. He taught some people and wrote many books on different aspects of philosophical sciences.

The philosophy of al-Kindi was strongly influenced by Neoplatonic Aristotelianism. He attempted to provide a philosophical basis for the speculative theology of the *Mutazilites*. Although he claimed that the conclusions of philosophy and religion are essentially harmonious, he nevertheless placed revelation above philosophy and prophetic insights above reason. Al-Kindi's influence on Muslim thinkers continued for about a century after his death.

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